

Wave load on a navigation lock sliding gate

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Abstract

The wave load on a navigation lock sliding gate equipped with a ballast tank is investigated assuming the linear wave theory is valid and using the eigenfunction expansion matching method to solve the governing equations. The correctness and the limits of the solution have been checked by comparing the results with those of a numerical code which solve the full non linear Navier-Stokes equations. The results relating to the effect of the geometrical parameters and wave characteristics on the load acting on the gate are presented and discussed.

The ballast tank is found to increase the complexity of the phenomenon in relation to the wave interaction with the gate. The results indicate that the peak value of the vertical force occurs for wave numbers mostly dependent on the tank length and on the tank position along the depth, while the thickness has a smaller influence. The ballast tank has also a significant effect on the horizontal dynamic force acting on the gate, which vanishes when the wave number takes particular values. Finally, the moment applied to the gate shows a dependency on the geometrical and hydrodynamic parameters similar to that of the forces.

Keywords: wave load, lock gate, eigenfunction expansion matching method,

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16 **1. Introduction**

17 Lock gates are essential parts of a navigation lock, since they allow for
18 the retention of water and the locking of vessels to a higher or lower level.
19 Several types of lock gates are used around the world: mitre gates, single
20 pivot gates, standing tainter gates, rolling gates, sliding gates, lift gates, etc.

21 Rolling and sliding gate for navigation locks are usually equipped with a
22 ballast tank, which allows the load on the roller carriages to be reduced in
23 order to improve the maneuverability. The presence of this element may pro-
24 duce some disadvantages, among which is the increase of vertical force due to
25 waves which may have negative effects especially during the gate movement.
26 Such a problem recently occurred in the seaside gate of the navigation lock
27 realized at the Malamocco inlet of the Venice lagoon which was designed to
28 allow the access to the Port of Venice during the operational period of the
29 flood control system Mo.S.E. This sliding gate is characterized by a verti-
30 cal plate on the lagoon side and a rack with a ballast tank on the sea side.
31 During a storm in 2015 the gate swung vertically due to the action of waves,
32 characterized by an incident wave height and mean period approximately
33 equal to 1 m and 8 s respectively. Ignoring the presence of the rack, as it
34 provides only a small contribution to the hydrodynamic forces, this gate may
35 be schematized as a totally immersed parallelepiped and a vertical wall ad-
36 jacent to it. The actions that waves exert on a similar structure were not
37 already analyzed in detail and no formulas or diagrams had been provided
38 that could be used for engineering purposes.

39 The vertical force induced by waves on horizontal deck has been widely
40 investigated but only for the case in which the horizontal deck is not im-
41 mersed. Kaplan and Silbert (1976), Kaplan (1992) and Kaplan et al. (1995)
42 investigated the wave forces acting on flat decks and horizontal beams on
43 offshore platforms. They developed a semi-analytic model for the evaluation
44 of time history wave loads on horizontal decks. Shih and Anastasiou (1992)
45 and Toumazis et al. (1989) analyzed wave-induced forces and pressures on
46 horizontal platform decks at small scales. Bea et al. (2001) proposed a semi-
47 empirical method which accounts for the dynamic amplification of slamming
48 due to dynamic response of structural elements. Tirindelli et al. (2002) and
49 McConnell et al. (2003) and McConnell et al. (2004) measured the wave loads
50 on deck and beam elements in a series of 2-dimensional physical model tests.
51 These measurements were carried out to explore the process of wave loading,
52 with the aim of developing improved predictions. Cuomo et al. (2003) and
53 Cuomo (2005) developed a new method for the analysis of non-stationary
54 time-history loads which is based on wavelet transform.

55 The influence of a vertical wall next to a deck near the coastline was
56 recently investigated by Kisacik et al. (2012a), Kisacik et al. (2012b) and
57 Kisacik et al. (2014) who analyzed the load conditions due to wave impacts
58 on a vertical structure with an overhanging horizontal cantilever slab.

59 Recently, Guo et al. (2015) analyzed the wave force acting on a semi-
60 submerged deck by using the potential flow approach. Such an approach is a
61 classic method to analyze the wave properties and wave force for structures
62 under gravity waves, such as elastic floating plates (Wu et al., 1995), a group
63 of submerged horizontal plates (Wang and Shen, 1999), and two layers of

64 horizontal thick plates (Liu et al., 2009). The approach has also been used
65 by Mei and Black (1969) and Black et al. (1971) to investigate the scattering
66 phenomenon and the wave force acting on submerged rectangular objects.

67 A configuration similar to the one considered in this paper was analyzed
68 by Wu et al. (1998) and Liu et al. (2007) in order to evaluate the perfor-
69 mance of a breakwater equipped with a submerged horizontal porous plate.
70 However, such studies were focused on the wave reflection of the breakwater
71 and only a thin plate was considered.

72 In the present paper the wave load acting on a navigation lock gate,
73 equipped with a prism-shaped tank connected to it at a certain height from
74 the bottom, is studied by means of an analytical solution of the wave field
75 obtained assuming the linear wave theory is valid and using the eigenfunction
76 expansion method to solve the boundary value problem. Since the solution
77 is based on the linear wave theory it cannot reproduce the nonlinear effect
78 of wave propagation . Therefore, in order to evaluate the correctness and
79 the limits of the theoretical model when the nonlinearities may be impor-
80 tant, the results have been compared with those obtained by means of the
81 numerical integration of the Navier-Stokes Equations (NSE). In section 2
82 the mathematical formulation of the boundary value problem is illustrated
83 and the eigenfunction expansion method is used to determine the analytical
84 solution. In section 3 a validation of the model is presented along with a
85 discussion about its limitations. In section 4 the analytical solution is used
86 to analyze the wave force induced on the gate for different geometrical config-
87 urations and hydrodynamic conditions. Finally, in section 5 the conclusions
88 are drawn.

89 **2. Formulation of the problem and analytical solution**

90 The flow generated by a progressive water wave propagating towards a
 91 navigation lock is here considered. Figure 1 shows a sketch of the problem.

Figure 1: Sketch of the problem.

92 The origin of the reference system is placed at the intersection between the
 93 still water level and the vertical wall. The x axis points in the direction of the
 94 incoming waves, while the z axis points upwards. It is assumed that the waves
 95 propagate in the direction orthogonal to the gate and that the latter have
 96 constant geometrical characteristics along the y axis of the reference system.
 97 Therefore, considering a structure infinitely extended in the y direction, the
 98 flow is two dimensional. It is assumed that the incoming wave is characterized
 99 by an amplitude $H/2$ much smaller than the wavelength L such that the
 100 linear potential wave theory can be applied (Mei et al., 2005). Denoting the
 101 velocity potential by the symbol Φ , the mathematical problem is posed by
 102 the Laplace equation plus appropriate boundary condition as reported below:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial z^2} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0 \quad \text{at the rigid boundaries,} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial t^2} + g \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial z} = 0 \quad \text{at } z=0, \quad (3)$$

103 where g is the gravity acceleration, t is the time and \mathbf{n} is the unit vector
 104 orthogonal to the boundary. Assuming that the incoming wave is sinusoidal
 105 with angular frequency σ , the potential can be written as $\Phi = Re(\phi e^{i\sigma t})$
 106 where i is the imaginary unit and ϕ is a new potential function depending on
 107 x and z . In terms of ϕ , the governing equations 1-3 can be written as follows

$$\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \mathbf{n}} = 0 \quad \text{at the rigid boundaries,} \quad (5)$$

$$-\sigma^2 \phi + g \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} = 0 \quad \text{at } z=0, \quad (6)$$

108 After ϕ has been determined, the pressure p is computed as follows:

$$p = -Re(i\sigma \rho \phi e^{i\sigma t}). \quad (7)$$

109 The mathematical problem posed by equations 4-6 has been solved by means
 110 of the eigenfunctions expansion matching method. The fluid domain has
 111 been divided into three regions as shown in Figure 1. Region Π_1 extends
 112 from $x = -b$ up to $x = -\infty$, region Π_2 is located below the ballast tank
 113 while region Π_3 is located above the ballast tank.

114 In region Π_1 the potential ϕ is given by the sum of three terms as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1 = & \frac{H g \cosh[k_1(z+h)]}{2 \sigma \cosh[k_1 h]} e^{-ik_1 x} + A_{11} \cosh[k_1(z+h)] e^{ik_1 x} + \\ & + \sum_{n=2}^N A_{1n} \cos[k_n(y+h)] e^{k_n x} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

115 The first term is the potential of the incoming wave, the second term is
 116 the potential due to the wave reflected by the gate and finally the third term
 117 is the potential of vanishing wave modes. The wavenumbers k_n satisfy the
 118 following dispersion relations:

$$\sigma^2 = gk_n \tanh(k_n h) \quad n = 1 \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma^2 = -gk_n \tan(k_n h) \quad n > 1 \quad (10)$$

119 It is worth to highlighting that equation 10 has infinite k_n solutions. In
 120 region Π_2 the potential ϕ can be written as follows:

$$\phi_2 = \sum_{n=1}^N A_{2n} \cos[\beta_n(z+h)] \cosh[\beta_n x], \quad (11)$$

121 where the wavenumbers β_n are given by the relations:

$$\beta_n = \frac{(n-1)\pi}{h_1} \quad (12)$$

122 where $h_1 = h - (d + s)$ (see Figure 1).

123 In region Π_3 the potential has the following expression:

$$\phi_3 = A_{31} \cosh[\lambda_1(z+d)] \cos[\lambda_1 x] + \sum_{n=2}^N A_{3n} \cos[\lambda_n(z+d)] \cosh[\lambda_n x] \quad (13)$$

124 where the wavenumbers λ_n satisfy the dispersion relations:

$$\sigma^2 = g\lambda_i \tanh(\lambda_i d) \quad i = 1 \quad (14)$$

$$\sigma^2 = -g\lambda_i \tan(\lambda_i d) \quad i > 1 \quad (15)$$

125 The potentials ϕ_1 , ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 given by equations 8, 11 and 13 respectively
 126 already satisfy the boundary conditions at the rigid walls (eq. 5), except at
 127 the vertical face of the ballast tank, and at the free surface (eq. 6).

128 The coefficient A_{ji} , that appear in equations 8, 11 and 13, are expansion
 129 coefficients whose values must be determined by matching the solutions per-
 130 tinent to the three regions along the strait line $x = -b$ shown in Figure 1.
 131 At $x = -b$ the matching of the velocity components in the x direction is
 132 imposed by means of the following equations:

$$\frac{\partial\phi_1}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial\phi_2}{\partial x} \quad -h \leq z \leq -(d+s) \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial\phi_1}{\partial x} = 0 \quad -(d+s) < z < -d \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial\phi_1}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial\phi_3}{\partial x} \quad -(h_1) \leq z \leq 0 \quad (18)$$

133 Multiplying equations 16-18 by $\cos[k_i(z+h)]$ (by $\cosh[k_i(z+h)]$ for $i = 1$),
 134 integrating over the respective domains of definition and adding together all
 135 the equations we obtain

$$\int_{-h}^0 \frac{\partial\phi_1}{\partial x} \cos[k_i(z+h)] dz = \int_{-h}^{-(d+s)} \frac{\partial\phi_2}{\partial x} \cos[k_i(z+h)] dz + \quad (19)$$

$$+ \int_{-d}^0 \frac{\partial\phi_3}{\partial x} \cos[k_i(z+h)] dz$$

136 Letting i vary from 1 to N and making use of the orthogonal properties
 137 of the functions $\cos[k_i(z+h)]$, N equations for the unknown coefficients are
 138 obtained. The left hand side of the i th equation 19 contains the unknown
 139 coefficient A_{1i} . In addition, for $i = 1$ the left hand side contains a known
 140 term due to the incoming wave. On right hand side of 19 all the unknown
 141 coefficients A_{2i} and A_{3i} appear.

142 The matching of the solutions between the regions Π_1 and Π_2 and between
 143 the regions Π_1 and Π_3 at $x = -b$ is expressed by the following equations:

$$\phi_2 = \phi_1 \quad -h \leq z \leq -(d+s) \quad (20)$$

$$\phi_3 = \phi_1 \quad -d \leq z \leq 0. \quad (21)$$

144 Equation 20 is multiplied by $\cos[\beta_n(z + h)]$ and equation 21 by $\cos[\lambda_i(z + d)]$
 145 (by $\cosh[\lambda_i(z + d)]$ for $i = 1$), then both equations are integrated over the
 146 respective domains of definition as follows,

$$\int_{-h}^{-(d+s)} \phi_2 \cos[\beta_i(z + h)] dz = \int_{-h}^{-(d+s)} \phi_1 \cos[\beta_i(z + h)] dz \quad (22)$$

$$\int_{-h_1}^0 \phi_3 \cos[\lambda_i(z + h)] dz = \int_{-h_1}^0 \phi_1 \cos[\lambda_i(z + h)] dz \quad (23)$$

147 Once again, making use of the orthogonal properties of the functions
 148 $\cos[\beta_i(z + h)]$ and $\cos[\lambda_i(z + h)]$ and letting i vary from 1 to N , equations
 149 22 and 23 produce N equations each. The terms on the left hand side of
 150 equations 22 and 23 contain unknown coefficients only while on the right
 151 hand side there are both unknown coefficients and known terms.

152 Overall, equations 19, 22 and 23 consist in a system of $3N$ equations
 153 whose solution provides the values of the $3N$ unknown coefficients. The
 154 solution of the linear systems has been carried out by means of the Gauss
 155 elimination approach.

156 After the values of the coefficients have been determined the hydrody-
 157 namic force acting on the lower and upper face of the ballast tank can be
 158 computed.

159 By using equation 7, the following expression for the force acting on the
 160 lower face of the ballast tank is obtained:

$$f_{v2} = -i\sigma\rho A_{21} \cos[\beta_n h_1] b - i\sigma\rho \sum_{n=2}^N A_{2n} \frac{1}{\beta_n} \cos[\beta_n h_1] \sinh[\beta_n b] \quad (24)$$

161 Analogously, the solution in region Π_3 , provides the following expression
 162 for the force acting on the upper face of the ballast tank:

$$f_{v3} = i\sigma\rho A_{31} \frac{\sin(\lambda_1 b)}{\lambda_1} + i\sigma\rho \sum_{n=2}^N A_{3n} \frac{\sinh(\lambda_n b)}{\lambda_n} \quad (25)$$

163 The horizontal force is the sum of the following components: the force
 164 acting on the surface that lies below the ballast tank denoted as f_{h2} , the
 165 force acting on the vertical face of the ballast tank denoted as f_{h1} and the
 166 force acting on the surface that lies above the ballast tank, denoted as f_{h3} .
 167 These forces have the following expressions:

$$f_{h2} = -i\sigma\rho A_{21} h_1 \quad (26)$$

$$f_{h1} = -i\rho \frac{1}{k_1} (\sinh[k_1(h-d)] - \sinh[k_1 h_1]) \left(g \frac{H}{2} \frac{e^{ik_1 b}}{\cosh[k_1 h]} + \sigma A_{11} e^{-ik_1 b} \right) \quad (27)$$

$$-i\sigma\rho \sum_{n=2}^N A_{1n} \frac{e^{-k_n b}}{k_n} (\sin[k_n(h-d)] - \sin[k_n h_1])$$

$$f_{h3} = -i\sigma\rho A_{31} \frac{\sinh[\lambda_1 d]}{\lambda_1} - i\sigma\rho \sum_{n=2}^N A_{3n} \frac{\sinh[\lambda_n d]}{\lambda_n} \quad (28)$$

168 When analyzing the gate stability under the action of the wave load, the
 169 moment produced by the pressure acting on the gate must also be considered.
 170 In the specific case, such moments can be distinguished into moments due
 171 to the pressure acting on the vertical walls and moments due to the pressure
 172 acting on the horizontal walls. The latter walls consist in the lower and
 173 upper face of the ballast tank. During the course of this work it has been

174 observed that under conditions of interest to engineering applications the
175 moment due to the wave load acting on the vertical walls is very close to
176 that produced in the absence of the ballast tank. Hence this moment is not
177 here presented. On the other hand the moments due to the dynamic pressure
178 acting on the lower and upper face of the ballast tank are here discussed in
179 view of their importance as concern the gate stability and also because these
180 moments depend on the geometrical and flow parameters in a complex way.
181 The moments are computed with respect to the point of coordinate $x = 0$
182 and $z = -h$. In the following the moment due to the pressure acting on the
183 lower face of the ballast tank is denoted as M_2 , while the moment due to the
184 pressure acting on the upper face is denoted as M_3 :

$$M_2 = -i\rho\sigma A_{21} \frac{b^2}{2} + i\rho\sigma \sum_{n=2}^N A_{2n} \cos[\beta_n h_1] \left[\frac{1}{\beta_n^2} (\cosh(\beta_n b) - 1) - \frac{\sinh(\beta_n b)}{\beta_n} \right] \quad (29)$$

$$M_3 = -i\rho\sigma A_{31} \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_1^2} (1 - \cos(\lambda_1 b)) - \frac{\sin(\lambda_1 b)b}{\lambda_1} \right] + \quad (30)$$

$$-i\rho\sigma \sum_{n=2}^N \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_n^2} (\cosh(\lambda_n b) - 1) - \frac{\sinh(\lambda_n b)b}{\lambda_n} \right]$$

185 In the previous equations the number N of eigenfunctions that appear in
186 the summation has been fixed to 100. Computations carried out by fixing
187 $N = 110$ provide results with negligible differences with respect to those
188 obtained by fixing $N = 100$.

189 **3. Validation and limits of the model**

190 In order to validate the model, a first comparison was made with the
 191 results of Wu et al. (1998). Figure 2 shows the amplitude of the dimensionless
 192 vertical force $|f_v^*| = |f_{v2} + f_{v3}|/(\rho \times g \times H \times b)$ versus b/L , for $d/h = 0.2$,
 193 $h/L = 0.25$ and $s/h = 0$ reported by Wu et al. (1998) and that computed by
 194 means of the present model. It can be observed that the two models provide
 195 indistinguishable results the one from each other.

Figure 2: Comparison between the dimensionless amplitude of the vertical force reported by Wu et al. (1998) and that computed by the present model for $d/h = 0.2$, $h/L = 0.25$ and $s/h = 0$.

196 Since the present model is based on the linear wave theory, it may fail
 197 when waves of no small amplitude are considered for which non linear effects
 198 can be important. In order to gain insights about the model error when wave
 199 nonlinearities are important, a comparison of the model results with those
 200 provided by the numerical integration of the Navier-Stokes equations (NSE)

201 has been carried out. More specifically, the integration of the NSE has been
202 carried out by means of the commercial software Flow-3D, produced by Flow
203 Science Inc. Flow-3D solves the Navier Stokes Equations (NSE) even in the
204 presence of a free surface. The numerical approach is based on a finite vol-
205 ume method on a structured Cartesian grid. The boundary conditions at the
206 free surface are introduced by means of the Volume of Fluid (VOF) condition
207 (Hirt and Nichols, 1981). In the present study the flow is 2D, therefore the
208 NSE have been solved by using a 2D structured Cartesian grid. In order
209 to optimize the spatial distribution of the mesh size the flow domain was
210 divided into four subdomains (see Figure 3) and in each of them a square
211 grid was adopted. The dimensionless resolution is $\Delta x/h = \Delta z/h = 0.0168$,
212 0.0084, 0.0042, and 0.0021 in subdomains A, B, C, D, respectively. To check
213 if the results change when the mesh size is decreased we carried out a numer-
214 ical simulation with a further subdomains around the ballast tank adopting
215 a mesh size equals to $\Delta x/h = \Delta z/h = 0.00105$, but this did not show sig-
216 nificant change in the magnitude of the force on the gate. In all the cases
217 the minimum mesh size was the one of subdomain adjacent to the ballast
218 tank and it is worth pointing out that this was too large to reproduce the
219 boundary layer along the surface of the gate and of the ballast tank. In-
220 deed the boundary has a thickness of the order of 1 cm while the minimum
221 mesh size is approximately 3 cm. Reducing the mesh size in order to de-
222 scribe the boundary layer would lead to the adoption of a huge grid and
223 to an uneconomical computation. An idea about the requirements of the
224 numerical grid to describe the boundary layer can be obtained through the
225 β parameter given by the equation $\beta = s^2/(\nu T)$, where s is the thickness

226 of the ballast tank and ν is the fluid viscosity. This parameter, along with
227 the Keulegan Carpenter number and the Reynolds number, is usually con-
228 sidered in studies of oscillatory flow around rigid bodies (see Scandura et al.,
229 2009). The square root of β is the ratio between the thickness of the ballast
230 tank s and the Stokes layer thickness $\sqrt{\nu T}$. Thus, it provides information on
231 the grid size necessary to solve the boundary layer around the body. In the
232 present numerical study, where a case that may occur in practical applica-
233 tion is considered ($s O(1)$ and $T O(10)$), the value of β is of order $10^5 - 10^6$.
234 This is very large value for β and prevents the possibility of simulating the
235 boundary layer around the ballast tank. Indeed previous numerical studies
236 on oscillatory flow around bodies have considered β parameters of several or-
237 der of magnitude smaller than the previous one (e.g. Zao and Cheng, 2014).
238 One of the consequences of not simulating the viscous boundary layer is that
239 even the vortex shedding phenomenon cannot be simulated. Even though
240 the forces arising from the viscous boundary layer are generally small and
241 can be neglected, the same is not valid for the forces induced by the vortex
242 shedding. Thus, it is relevant to provide an explanation of why the numerical
243 simulations provide reliable results regarding the force acting on the ballast
244 tank even though the vortex shedding is not correctly reproduced. The jus-
245 tification is based on the Keulegan Carpenter number KC which is given by
246 the expression $KC = u_0 T / s$, where u_0 is the undisturbed amplitude of the
247 velocity oscillations near to the ballast tank. This dimensionless number is
248 the ratio between the fluid particles displacement and the size of the ballast
249 tank. When the KC number is smaller than 1, the shed vortices are weak
250 and move along a very limited portion of the body, thus they provide a small

251 contribution to the total force. On the basis of the wave characteristics here
 252 considered, close to the ballast tank $u_0 \approx 0.2$ m/s, hence $KC < 1$. Then the
 253 vortex shedding provides a very small contribution to the force acting on the
 254 ballast tank, which is instead dominated by the inertia force, related to fluid
 255 acceleration. In summary for the present set of parameters even numerical
 256 simulations that do not capture the boundary layer provide reliable results
 257 as concerns the hydrodynamic force.

Figure 3: Sketch of domain adopted for CFD computation.

258 Figure 4 shows the comparison between the results obtained by means
 259 of the analytical model and those provided by the numerical solution of the
 260 NSE for a fixed geometry and different wave characteristics. The compari-
 261 son was carried out by fixing $d/h = 0.327$, $b/h = 0.269$, and $s/h = 0.236$.
 262 Two parameters mainly affect the wave non linearity i.e.: the wave num-
 263 ber $kh = 2\pi h/L$ and the wave slope H/L . The comparison shows that the
 264 present model reproduces quite well the vertical force induced on the bal-
 265 last tank for waves characterized by small non-linearity ($kh = 1.761$ and
 266 $H/L = 0.009$). For a fixed value of kh the agreement between the peaks of

267 the wave force worsens when H/L increases. In particular when the non-
268 linearity increases the model underestimates the positive peak value of the
269 dimensionless vertical force and overestimates the negative peak. The max-
270 imum underestimation is equal to approximately 19% for $kh = 0.859$ and
271 $H/L = 0.019$ while the maximum overestimation of the negative peak is
272 approximately 14% for $kh = 1.310$ and $H/L = 0.019$. It can be also ob-
273 served that for small kh , increasing H/L the phase at which the negative
274 peak occurs shift back while the phase of the positive peak shift forward.

275 Although Figure 4 shows some discrepancies between model predictions
276 and the NSE solution the theoretical model is appropriate for carrying out
277 a detailed investigation of the wave load on the gate as these discrepancies
278 are acceptable in the range of the parameters investigated. This is particu-
279 larly advantageous as such a kind of investigation would involve prohibitive
280 computational costs if carried out by means of integration of the NSE.

281 4. Discussion of model results

282 The dimensionless amplitude of the vertical force $|f_v^*|$ acting on the ballast
283 tank, is shown in Figure 5 versus kh for several values of the ratios d/h , s/h ,
284 and b/h . For all the analyzed conditions a peak value of $|f_v^*|$ is detected. The
285 results show a decrease of $|f_v^*|$ when the relative depth d/h of the upper face
286 of the ballast tank increases. The peak value of $|f_v^*|$ occurs for value of kh
287 mostly dependent on b/h and d/h , while s/h has a small effect in the range
288 of values here considered.

289 Generally, the lower the ratio b/h , the higher the value kh at which the
290 maximum of the dimensionless force is detected. This can be explained by

Figure 4: Comparison between the force acting on the ballast tank computed by means of the numerical integration of the NSE and that computed by means of the present model: $d/h = 0.327$, $b/h = 0.269$ and $s/h = 0.236$.

291 noting that in order to have a strong interaction between waves and ballast
 292 tank the relation $L \sim \xi b$ must be satisfied, where ξ is a coefficient larger than
 293 1 but not much larger than 1. Indeed, for $L \gg b$ the wave sees the gate as
 294 a plane wall, therefore the vertical force is very small. This can be checked
 295 by noting the ratio b/L is proportional to $kh \times b/h$ and observing that in
 296 Figure 5 when this ratio tends to zero the vertical force is very small.

Figure 5: Dimensionless amplitude of the vertical force versus the relative depth kh .

297 The case $L \ll b$ is out of practical applications as in general b is of the
 298 order of a meter and L is of the order of ten meters. However, assuming

299 that the condition $L \ll b$ is true, it is expected that the pressure over
300 the ballast tank oscillates several times around zero such that the overall
301 contribution to the force becomes small or even vanishes for particular values
302 of the parameters. Indeed, the condition $L \ll b$ can be written as $b/L =$
303 $(kh/2\pi) \times b/h \gg 1$ and it can be observed in Figure 5 that when kh and b/h
304 are both large the force is small. Therefore, being $L \sim \xi b$ we immediately
305 get $kh \sim 1/(\xi b/h)$ which shows that when b/h increases the value at which
306 the peak of the force occurs shift at lower values as shown in Figure 5.

307 The condition $L > d$, in general necessary to have interaction between
308 waves and ballast tank, can be written as $kh < 1/(d/h)$. In much of the
309 cases shown in figure 5 the maximum of the force occurs for values of kh
310 that are significantly smaller than $1/(d/h)$. Therefore in these cases it is not
311 necessary that when d/h increases the value of kh , at which the maximum
312 occurs, decreases. However, for small values of b/h it can be observed in
313 Figure 5 that the maximum is found at large values of kh which are close to
314 the limits imposed by the relation $kh < 1/(d/h)$. Therefore in these cases
315 when d/h increase the maximum shift at lower values of kh .

316 The influence of the relative thickness of the ballast tank s/h is smaller
317 than those related to other geometrical parameters. Indeed, the results show
318 that a variation of one order of magnitude in the ratio s/h can produce a
319 difference of $|f_v^*|$ in the range 15-30%.

320 Figures 6-8 summarize results that can be useful for engineering applica-
321 tion: for a fixed geometrical configuration the peak value of the dimensionless
322 vertical force acting on the gate and the wave number at which it is detected
323 are reported. The figures show that the value of kh at which the peak value

324 of $|f_v^*|$ is detected increases with d/h for large value of b/h while it decrease
 325 for small value of b/h . Comparing figures 6, 7 and 8 it can be observed that
 326 the peak value of the force increases with s/h while the value of kh at which
 327 such a peak occurs shifts at lower values.

Figure 6: Maximum value of the dimensionless amplitude of vertical force for $s/h = 0.00$:
 a) dimensionless value of the vertical force; b) value of kh at which the peak is detected.

Figure 7: Maximum value of the dimensionless amplitude of vertical force for $s/h = 0.11$:
 a) dimensionless value of the vertical force; b) value of kh at which the peak is detected.

Figure 8: Maximum value of the dimensionless amplitude of vertical force for $s/h = 0.22$: a) dimensionless value of the vertical force; b) value of kh at which the peak is detected.

328 As regards the dimensionless horizontal dynamic force $|f_h^*| = |f_{h1} + f_{h2} +$
 329 $f_{h3}|/(\rho \times g \times H \times b)$ acting on the gate, it is significantly affected by the
 330 ballast tank. Indeed, in Figure 9, where the amplitude of the dimensionless
 331 horizontal force acting on the gate is reported as a function of kh and for
 332 different value of b/h , it can be observed that for $d/h < 0.37$ the amplitude
 333 of the force vanishes when kh takes particular values, while this results is
 334 not observed for $b/h = 0$ (absence of ballast tank). Furthermore, it can be
 335 observed that the presence of the ballast tank mostly produces a decrease of
 336 $|f_h^*|$ with respect to the case of a vertical wall.

337 In order to explain why the horizontal dynamic force may vanish, it is
 338 useful to analyze separately the force acting on the upper and lower portions
 339 of the gate. Figure 10 shows that the horizontal force $|f_{h3}^*| = |f_{h3}|/(\rho \times g \times$
 340 $H \times b)$ acting on the upper gate portion never vanishes and that it is only
 341 slightly affected by the parameters d/h , s/h , and b/h for large value of kh .

342 On the contrary, the horizontal force acting on the lower gate portion

343 $|f_{h2}^*| = |f_{h2}|/(\rho \times g \times H \times b)$, shown in Figure 11, has a much larger os-
 344 cillating behavior and vanishes when kh takes particular values. Note that
 345 according to equation (26) these values are those for which the coefficient A_{21}
 346 vanishes. Indeed, the other coefficients do not contribute to the force because
 347 their associated eigenfunctions have a purely oscillating behaviour. The cor-
 348 rectness of this result was checked by means of the numerical solution of the
 349 NSE (see Figure 12) by investigating the behaviour of the force in a neigh-
 350 borhood of the value of kh that according to the model provides a vanishing
 351 value of the force. It can be observed that there is a reasonable agreement
 352 between the model and the numerical simulations. The differences may be
 353 attributed to the wave non linearities which are not taken into account in
 354 the model.

355 Vanishing of $|f_{h2}^*|$ corresponds to a 180 degree variation of phase oscilla-
 356 tion. Therefore, since the force acting on the upper portion does not change
 357 phase, when adding together all the contributions to the horizontal force the
 358 sum may vanishes for certain values of kh .

359 As regards the moment of the vertical forces, Figure 13 shows the am-
 360 plitude of the dimensionless momentum acting on the ballast tank $|m_v^*| =$
 361 $|m_v|/(\rho \times g \times H \times b^2)$ with respect to the foot of the gate, for several values of
 362 the ratios d/h , s/h , and b/h . A decrease of $|m_v^*|$ is observed when the relative
 363 depth d/h of the upper face of the ballast tank increases. Furthermore, the
 364 peak value of $|m_v^*|$ occurs for values of kh mostly dependent on b/h and d/h .
 365 The parameter s/h has a smaller effect which becomes more significant for
 366 small values of b/h .

367 Figures 14-16 show, for a fixed geometrical configuration, the peak value

Figure 9: Dimensionless amplitude of the horizontal force acting on the whole gate versus the relative depth kh .

Figure 10: Dimensionless amplitude of the horizontal force acting on the upper gate portion versus the relative depth kh .

Figure 11: Dimensionless amplitude of the horizontal force acting on the lower gate portion versus the relative depth kh .

Figure 12: Dimensionless amplitude of the horizontal force acting on the lower gate portion versus the relative depth kh - Comparison with Flow-3D results: $d/h = 0.37$, $b/h = 0.314$ and $s/h = 0$.

368 of $|m_v^*|$ and the wave number at which it is detected. The results repeat the
 369 same behavior described for the vertical force acting on the ballast tank.

370 Finally, as reported in section 2 the analyses showed that in the range of
 371 the parameters of engineering interest, the moment of the horizontal force is
 372 always smaller than that acting on the gate without ballast tank.

373 5. Conclusions

374 The wave load on a navigation lock sliding gate equipped with a ballast
 375 tank has been investigated by means of an analytical solution based on the
 376 linear wave theory. In addition for several different values of the parameters
 377 the wave loads have been calculated by means of numerical integration of
 378 the Navier-Stokes equations and the results have been used to gain insights
 379 into the importance of the flow nonlinearities and into the accuracy of the

Figure 13: Dimensionless amplitude of the momentum due to the vertical forces versus the relative depth kh .

Figure 14: Maximum value of the dimensionless amplitude of moment of vertical force for $s/h = 0.00$: a) dimensionless value of the vertical force; b) value of kh at which the peak is detected.

Figure 15: Maximum value of the dimensionless amplitude of moment of vertical force for $s/h = 0.11$: a) dimensionless value of the vertical force; b) value of kh at which the peak is detected.

380 analytical solution. It has been shown that because of the nonlinearities the
 381 analytical solution is affected by an error of the order of 10% in the range
 382 of the parameters investigated. This is reasonable for engineering application

Figure 16: Maximum value of the dimensionless amplitude of moment of vertical force for $s/h = 0.22$: a) dimensionless value of the vertical force; b) value of kh at which the peak is detected.

383 and justify the use of the analytical solution for the computation of the
 384 wave load. The results show that the presence of the ballast tank produces
 385 both significant vertical force and an important alteration of the horizontal
 386 dynamic load.

387 The peak values of the dimensionless amplitude of the vertical forces $|f_v^*|$
 388 and of its moment $|m_v^*|$ occur for values of kh mostly dependent on the rela-
 389 tive length b/h and depth d/h . As concerns the effect of the relative thickness
 390 s/h of the ballast tank it does not have an important effect when b/h is large
 391 while it becomes more important for smaller values of b/h . Generally, the
 392 lower the ratio b/h , the higher the value of kh at which the maximum of
 393 $|f_v^*|$ and $|m_v^*|$ are detected and the lower are $|f_v^*|$ and $|m_v^*|$. An increase of
 394 the relative depth d/h of the upper edge of the ballast tank, for large b/h in
 395 addition to reducing the peak force, produces an increase of the value of kh
 396 at which such a peak is detected while the opposite occurs for small b/h .

397 The proposed analytical solution also shows that the ballast tank pro-
398 duces a significant variation of the dimensionless horizontal dynamic force
399 acting on the gate, which could vanish for particular values of kh . Such be-
400 havior is due to the fact that the oscillations of the force acting on the lower
401 portion of the gate may become 180 degrees out of phase with respect to
402 the forces acting on the upper portion and on the vertical face of the ballast
403 tank. Therefore the total force may vanish.

404 Finally, the relation between the amplitude of the force acting on the
405 gate and the geometrical parameters is summarized in diagrams that can be
406 useful for engineering purpose.

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415 **References**

416 Bea, R., Iversen, R., and Xu, T. (2001). Wave-in-deck forces on offshore plat-
417 forms. *Journal of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering*, 123(1):10–
418 21.

- 419 Black, J., Mei, C., and Bray, M. (1971). Radiation and scattering of water
420 waves by rigid bodies. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 46(1):151–164.
- 421 Cuomo, G. (2005). Dynamics of wave-induced loads and their effects on
422 coastal structures. *Dynamics of Wave-induced Loads and Their Effects on*
423 *Coastal Structures*.
- 424 Cuomo, G., Allsop, N., and McConnell, K. (2003). Dynamic wave loads on
425 coastal structures: analysis of impulsive and pulsating wave loads. *Proc.*
426 *Conf. Coastal Structures 2003*, pages 356–368.
- 427 Guo, A., Fang, Q., and Li, H. (2015). Analytical solution of hurricane wave
428 forces acting on submerged bridge decks. *Ocean Engineering*, 108:519–528.
- 429 Hirt, C. and Nichols, B. (1981). Volume of fluid (vof) method for the dy-
430 namics of free boundaries. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 39(1):201 –
431 225.
- 432 Kaplan, P. (1992). Wave impact forces on offshore structures: Re-
433 examination and new interpretations. *Proc., Offshore Technol. Conf.*,
434 pages 79–86.
- 435 Kaplan, P., Murray, J., and Yu, W. (1995). Theoretical analysis of wave
436 impact forces on platform deck structures. volume 1, pages 189–198.
- 437 Kaplan, P. and Silbert, M. (1976). Impact forces on platform horizontal
438 members in the splash zone. *Offshore Technology Conference*, pages 749–
439 758.

- 440 Kisacik, D., Troch, P., and Van Bogaert, P. (2012a). Description of loading
441 conditions due to violent wave impacts on a vertical structure with an
442 overhanging horizontal cantilever slab. *Coastal Engineering*, 60(1):201–
443 226.
- 444 Kisacik, D., Troch, P., and Van Bogaert, P. (2012b). Experimental study of
445 violent wave impact on a vertical structure with an overhanging horizontal
446 cantilever slab. *Ocean Engineering*, 49:1–15.
- 447 Kisacik, D., Troch, P., Van Bogaert, P., and Caspeele, R. (2014). Inves-
448 tigation of uplift impact forces on a vertical wall with an overhanging
449 horizontal cantilever slab. *Coastal Engineering*, 90:12–22.
- 450 Liu, Y., Li, Y.-c., and Teng, B. (2007). Wave interaction with a perforated
451 wall breakwater with a submerged horizontal porous plate. *Ocean Engi-
452 neering*, 34(17-18):2364–2373.
- 453 Liu, Y., Li, Y.-c., and Teng, B. (2009). Wave motion over two submerged
454 layers of horizontal thick plates. *Journal of Hydrodynamics*, 21(4):453–462.
- 455 McConnell, K., Allsop, N., Cuomo, G., and Cruickshank, I. (2003). New
456 guidance for wave forces on jetties in exposed locations. *Paper to Conf.
457 COPEDEC VI, Colombo, Sri Lanka*, page 20.
- 458 McConnell, K., Allsop, W., and Cruickshank, I. (2004). *Piers, Jetties and
459 Related Structures Exposed to Waves - Guidelines for Hydraulic Loadings*.
- 460 Mei, C. and Black, J. (1969). Scattering of surface waves by rectangular
461 obstacles in waters of finite depth. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 38(pt
462 3):499–511.

- 463 Mei, C., Stiassnie, M., and Yue, D. (2005). *Theory and applications of ocean*
464 *surface waves. Part 1: Linear Aspects*. World Scientific.
- 465 Scandura, P., Armenio, V., and Foti, E. (2009). Numerical investigation of
466 the oscillatory flow around a circular cylinder close to a wall at moderate
467 KeuleganCarpenter and low Reynolds numbers. *Journal of Fluid Mechan-*
468 *ics*, 627:259–290.
- 469 Shih, R. and Anastasiou, K. (1992). Laboratory study of the wave-induced
470 vertical loading on platform decks. *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil*
471 *Engineers: Water, Maritime and Energy*, 96(1):19–33.
- 472 Tirindelli, M., McConnell, K., Allsop, N., and Cuomo, G. (2002). Exposed
473 jetties: Inconsistencies and gaps in design methods for wave-induced forces.
474 *Proc. 28th ICCE, Cardiff, UK*, pages 1684–1696.
- 475 Toumazis, A., Shih, W., and Anastasiou, K. (1989). Wave impact loading on
476 horizontal and vertical plates. *Proc. of IAHR 89 Conf., Ottawa, Canada*,
477 pages c209–c216.
- 478 Wang, K.-H. and Shen, Q. (1999). Wave motion over a group of submerged
479 horizontal plates. *International Journal of Engineering Science*, 37(6):703–
480 715.
- 481 Wu, C., Watanabe, E., and Utsunomiya, T. (1995). An eigenfunction
482 expansion-matching method for analyzing the wave-induced responses of
483 an elastic floating plate. *Applied Ocean Research*, 17(5):301–310.
- 484 Wu, J., Wan, Z., and Fang, Y. (1998). Wave reflection by a vertical wall with
485 a horizontal submerged porous plate. *Ocean Engineering*, 25(9):767–779.

486 Zao, M., and Cheng, L. (2014). Two-dimensional numerical study of vortex
487 shedding regimes of oscillatory flow past two circular cylinders in side-by-
488 side and tandem arrangements at low Reynolds numbers. *Journal of Fluid*
489 *Mechanics*, 751:1–37.